

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Narrow Concept of Accountability in Public Sector Expenditure: Measuring Accountability Proportionately and Progressively

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Abstract

Accountability is one of the main elements of the realization of good governance which is currently being pursued in Indonesia. The government is asked to report the results of the programs that have been implemented so that the public can assess whether the government has worked economically, efficiently and effectively. Accountability can be seen from an accounting perspective, a functional perspective and an accountability system perspective. This Scientific Journal uses normative legal research and uses a statutory approach and a legal concept approach. the development of the public service paradigm from a broad concept of accountability to a narrow concept of accountability in public sector procurement spending that uses providers of goods and services, both as business entities and individuals, is done through the selection of providers of goods and services. The power to set policies is exercised by the legislature, specifically in the policy of setting the state budget, known as budget rights. Meanwhile, the executive power in the field of state finances is known as the general power for managing state finances. Based on this, the concept of governance which emphasizes the mechanism in carrying out functions by actors involved in certain sectors has not shown a certain mechanism, as well as the principle of accountability which is an element of governance that is still an accountability concept with general evaluative character (umbrella concept). The very broad, general and evaluative, is very difficult to define practically and empirically because there are no operational standards for accountable behavior.

Keywords: Accountability, Good Governance, Public Sector Expenditure

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1. Introduction

Along with the adoption of the concept of governance in the administration of government, the management of the public sector has undergone significant developments and paradigm shifts. Many thoughts from public sector management experts who discuss this new paradigm, such as David Osborne and Ted Gaebler in their work Reinventing Government or entrepreneurship bureaucracy (Sugiyarti 2015), as well as the thoughts of Colin Talbot in his Theories of Performance: Organizational and Service Improvement in the Public Domain (Talbot 2010), In addition, starting in the 1990s, the science of public administration introduced a new paradigm which is often called the New Public Management (NPM). Although it is also called by other names such as Post-bureaucratic Paradigm by Barzeley,

but in general it will be called NPM again because it departs from Christopher Hood's idea as the beginning of an alternative paradigm (Akbar 2015). Based on the developments of some of these thinkers, it is shown that along with the increasing role of the private sector and society in the administration of the economy and participation in making public policies, it demands a flexible, dynamic, effective-efficient and accountable public sector management for the performance of the outputs produced in the implementation of management. public sector. With the dynamics of implementing regional autonomy in Indonesia as it is currently being implemented, the central government to local governments are currently preparing for the preparation of a better government accounting standard as well as intensive discussions on the role of public